

Prostitution in India: From 'Ritual Servitude' to
'Modern Sex Work'

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By
TANAY V REDDY
[252EPS037]

Under the Supervision of
Dr Maria A
Coordinator - Dept of Sociology

ST JOSEPH'S UNIVERSITY
Bangalore

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Introduction

Kingsley Davis defined Prostitution as 'That form of Sexual Behaviour which has its end in itself, and is engaged in without emotional involvement, and for which Payment is made'. (Kingsley Davis, 1937)

Many Sociologists see Prostitution as a Social Institution which is created due to Economic Inequalities, Patriarchy, and Urbanization.

Prostitution in India isn't anything new as it existed since the birth of society. It existed in many hidden forms since the past, Modernization and Urbanization made it more open and seen to the world.

The pressure from the Social Elements and their desires act as a catalyst in triggering the Sexual Transgression of Females (Divya R, 2025).

It was only limited to women since many centuries but in the present-day world it has expanded to men, and transgenders too.

How It Came into Existence?

It is often called as the Oldest Profession of the world. Early Primitive Societies did not have the Institution of Marriage which we know about today and Sexual Relations were Communal. As societies became organized, restrictions were imposed through Marriage, Kinship, and Inheritance Systems and Widow Women, Slaves and Poor Women who were not added into the system of Society remained outside these systems started engaging in Sexual Exchange with Men for their Survival

Sinha and Basu (1933) trace Prostitution in Ancient India as a Social Institution which has remained in existence since many centuries rather than just a marginal practice. In early Vedic Societies, Courtesans (Ganika's, Nagar Vadhus) were not just mere sexual figures who were skilled in Dance and Music, they enjoyed the prestige of Royal Courts and also received gifts from Rulers and Subjects too. Texts like Arthashastra describe how these Courtesans were treated equally as other subjects and also paid taxes which contributed to the economy of the kingdom.

Devadasi System:

The devadasi system is a social-cultural practice that exists mostly in the southern states of India and is believed to have originated between 6th and 7th Century. The term

'devadasi' means 'female slave of god' (Tarachand, 1992). It is said that these devadasis served gods and later men, as their slaves and considered it as an honour (Vishwanathan, 2008).

The devadasi system is a social and religious practice of dedicating young girls to Hindu temples in India (Shingal, 2015). A girl belonging to a Dalit community is married off to a Hindu deity and is asked to serve the god {her husband} and the temple {her home}.

Altekar (1959) defines the devadasi system as:

'When temples of Hindu gods came to be built and endowed on a magnificent scale, some people began to feel in course of time that there should be singing girls attached to shrines to play music on the occasions of the different services and worships of the day... The introduction of dancing girls in temples tended to lower their moral and spiritual atmosphere. Some people began to visit shrines not so much to pay their respect to the deities, as to carry on their love intrigues with the singing girls employed there'.

As a result, these girls are sexually exploited and are raped by temple priests, people belonging to dominant castes and devotees as well. After a certain age, when these girls are not considered 'ideal' for temple service they are abandoned to lead a life full of humiliation. With no other choice they turn to Prostitution to earn their living as no one else marries them or supports them economically (Orchard 2007).

Due to economic problems families dedicate their young girls as devadasis and after a certain period of time these former devadasis dedicate their daughters as devadasis entering a practice of a never ending inter-generational cycle (Amit Anand,2024).

The devadasi practice, unfortunately, has also become a means for poor Dalit families to unburden themselves of their daughters (Harishankar and Priyamvada, 2016)

The devadasi system is an exploitative social practice that targets the most vulnerable section of women in the Indian society, i.e., Dalit women. Because of this practice young Dalit girls are sexually abused and exploited forcing them to join in 'Commercial sexual activity' i.e., Prostitution.

Religious practices such as Devadasi system tied Prostitution to Temple Service making it a 'Sacred job' and the prostitute a 'Sacred Body' even while they were being exploited by 'devotees'.

Furthermore, during the Medieval period, temples began getting huge donations first from kings and later from landlords and as a result, they gradually assumed the status of social-financial institutions (Mishra and Rao, 2005). Time by time as the temple's hundi started filling, the priests felt that they should start performing more rituals and increase the area of the temple, but they needed more servants to take care of the property. This led to the temple recruiting many girls as servants who not only worked as slaves but danced and sung during religious occasions too.

Prostitution In Ancient India {by the Arthashastra}

Ancient India was not an exception to the institution of prostitution and it gave impetus to a systematically organized institute of harlots. Chanakya regarded prostitution as a profitable profession and outlined the duties and activities of prostitutes in the Arthashastra but was silent about their connection with the temple devadasis

These prostitutes were divided into 3 categories:

- a) Royal Prostitutes
 - b) City-Level Prostitutes
 - c) Private Prostitute or a group of prostitutes under the control of a Private Person
- and all 3 of these classes were under the control of the state

These 'Prostitutes' were called as Pratiganika, Rupajiva, Vesya, Dasi, Devadasi, Punchsali, Silpakarika, which meant special kinds/ higher level prostitutes. A superintendent known as Ganikadhyaksha was placed who had to keep an eye on the prostitutes and make sure they make payments and gifts to the state. He also had a duty to limit their earnings and inheritance (Aya), daily expenses.

Arthasastra also gives us a gist of the bio data of these prostitutes

Freedom for these prostitutes weren't given for free of cost, they had to make a payment of 24,000 Panas as a ransom to the state. As they were servants of the state, the state would lose its income if prostitutes were given freedom to walk away. (G. Kuppuram, 1979)

The Period of Transition/Change:

Devadasis who were married off to temples and were exploited slowly started learning that they could earn their bread not only through the temples funds but also by selling their body which slowly started them making the temple surroundings as a brothel house and there was an increase in customers and not devotees. These so-called devadasis now completely began to be known by the modern term 'Prostitutes'. With the decline of kingdoms due to wars and natural calamities, Courtesans/Ganika's lost their economic support and they were stripped off patronage and were left without a livelihood, so they gradually started maintaining sexual relationships with wealthy men outside the temple/Kingdom for their survival. Over time the ritual dedication of their body became symbolic while their sexual exploitation gradually started increasing.

It was later by the British Regime that these forms of entertainment were regarded as signs of Sexual Depravity in the natives. The nautch girl became a detestable category and her performance, amorous and vulgar. (Shabad Bano, 2009-2010)

Prostitution In Modern Day India: Focus on Ghegholi

Sex work is a way of life of thousands and lakhs of women in lower caste communities in Rural India. They are born into a traditional system of sex trade-only few make it out of it.

Prostitution is the oldest profession of the world and is prevalent in India since many centuries. With sex work being legal in India there are an estimated number of 3 Million sex workers in India between the ages 15-35.

In the village of Ghegholi in the Alwar district of Rajasthan women of Nats, Bhedia, and Kanjar nomadic tribes are bound by an old caste system which follows prostitution as a tradition.

Before they were driven into sex work they played as performers, dancers, jugglers and magicians and were viewed as a threat by the British Colonial Power.

These women stand at the road dressed up waiting for customers to feed their families and kids. They are driven into this field not only due to tradition but also due to Poverty, Debt and call it a Profession by Choice. As banks do not lend money as they do not consider sex work as work, these families turn to local money lenders who charge exuberant interest rates landing them in a vicious cycle.

Due to presence of Social Stigma and superstitions, and are not able to make it out of this vicious cycle and wait for a ray of light which would bring them out of this cycle.

Red Light Areas in India:

The operation of brothels in India is officially prohibited (De Jure), but still, they are in operation in specific areas. India's largest and best-known red-light districts are:

Sonagachi, Kolkata: It is Asia's Largest red-light district with nearly 10000-16000 female sex workers working in the area.

Kamathipura, Mumbai: It is Second Largest red-light district in India with around 5000 sex workers approximately

Budhwar Peth, Pune: India's third largest red-light district with around 5000 sex workers working under 700 brothels

Chaturbhuj Sthan, Muzaffarpur: It is a red-light district in Bihar with around 3500 sex workers.

Other Red-Light Districts are G. B. Road in Delhi, and Ganga Jamuna in Nagpur. Girls of both Legal and Juvenile ages are dragged and forced into these brothel houses due to Poverty, Lack of Food/Shelter and even orphans sometimes are dragged into this business.

Conclusion

In Summary, Socio-Cultural norms in Indian society reinforce patriarchal values with the devadasi system and prostitution emerging as a product of multiple interlocking factors that constitute structural violence against women. They were and are still trapped in a cycle of no end. The society of India even after knowing that their husbands and wives are indulging in these practices for sexual satisfaction still view this way of life as 'Dirty'.

Prostitution wasn't something which emerged on its own, it was created by the society for the society

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